

ADAPTATION OF ENGLISH METHODOLOGICAL TERMS TO NATIONAL VARIANTS IN THE TERMINOLOGICAL CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the process of adapting widely used terms within the methodology of teaching English to national variants in the Uzbek language. The main emphasis is on the formation of a suitable terminological environment in accordance with the national education system and cultural environment. The article also considers problems arising in translation, criteria for selecting equivalents of terms, and localization strategies.

In the modern educational process, the English language is distinguished by its global importance. In particular, hundreds of terms have been created in the field of language teaching methodologies, which are widely used in international standards. However, the adaptation of these terms to national variants in the Uzbek language is often far from uniform. This article is devoted to proposing a solution to this problem and analyzing methodological approaches to forming a national terminological environment.

The acceleration of globalization processes, the increase in international cooperation and international relations, new ideas arising from the intersection of various scientific fields, as well as the increasingly deep penetration of information and communication technologies into our lives, are the basis for the wide-scale formation of modern terms. Integration processes in the field of science, education and technology are creating the basis for the expansion of the system of terms for each field, the naming of new concepts and phenomena.

At the same time, scientific research in various fields, the rise of scientific development to a new level, in turn, requires the creation of new terms. This in itself indicates the need to expand the scope of terminological research in modern linguistics. The increase in vocabulary in any language occurs, first of all, due to terms expressing new concepts. As new terms enter the language system, they add a new semantic load to existing lexical units, and in some cases enter the language as a completely new lexical unit.

In particular, such processes are clearly felt in the field of education. Today, the need to express new concepts that have arisen within the framework of pedagogical activity, educational technologies and methodological approaches is leading to the development of terms related to this area. New scientific terms that express human intellectual potential, creative activity, and achievements in the educational process are contributing to the enrichment of the terminological base in this area.

At the same time, the vocabulary of the Uzbek language is being replenished with new pedagogical terms by introducing terms that are actively used in the international educational arena into the national education system. This requires a deep analysis not only of the translation process, but also of their semantic adaptation, structural integration, and methodological features.

The linguistic approach to terms poses a number of complex tasks. Within the framework of this approach, it is important to study the role of terms in the language, their lexical-semantic and grammatical structure, their compliance with the scientific method, as well as their compliance with international terminological rules. Also, the study of terminology systems, their classification and standardization using modern technologies is emerging as one of the current problems in linguistics.

Thus, the development of terminology once again confirms that language is a changing and flexible system. Each new concept, discovery in a new scientific field or technological innovation forms a system of terms corresponding to it, which becomes an integral part of language development.

Also, terminological systems are formed on a global scale and are enriched in the process of assimilation from one language to another. Terms created in one language and actively used in scientific and technical fields are assimilated into other languages, serving to expand their lexical reserve. This situation is directly related to the dynamic, changing and assimilating nature of the language. In particular, many pedagogical terms have entered the Uzbek language from other languages, and today they are actively used in our education system, becoming an internalized phenomenon in terms of understanding and application. Therefore, these terms can be considered as full-fledged lexical units of the Uzbek language.

Pedagogical terms existing in the Uzbek language and adopted from foreign languages are interpreted within the framework of the educational sphere through their semantic fields. Their content and functions in the language are analyzed in depth at the level of lexicology and syntax, which are one of the main areas of linguistics. The meaning of a word, its contextual use, stylistic features, morphological structure and grammatical function are of particular importance for linguistic research. In particular, semantic analysis of terms is an important tool in the systematic study of language.

From the point of view of in-depth study of terminology, it is not enough to consider terms only at the lexicographic level. After all, terms are also considered as language units in a general sense - lexical units. Therefore, they require comprehensive study not only at the lexical, but also at the grammatical, semantic and stylistic levels. Terms have their own linguistic characteristics, which distinguish them from other units in the language.

1. Field specialization of terms. Terms, as a rule, arise in a specialized field of science, technology, industry, art, medicine, agriculture, economics, law, military affairs and others. They serve to express special concepts in these fields. For example, terms used in the fields of "hydraulics", "linguistics", "political science", "geography", "jurisprudence" — such as "hydrolocation", "syntax", "political discourse", "demarcation", "constitutionalism" — were formed precisely based on the needs of these disciplines.

2. Terms should be clear, concise and understandable. Terms are mainly created to express special concepts clearly, briefly and concisely. They have an explanatory, strictly

defined meaning. For example, “hydrolocation” (Greek “hydro” - water, Latin “locatio” - location) is a technological process carried out using natural or artificial acoustic waves to identify underwater objects. This term is specific, concrete, and clearly expresses the concept within the framework of science. This technology is of great importance in areas such as naval warfare, fisheries, oceanographic research, and disaster relief.

3. The semantic nature of terms (monosemanticity). In theory, terms should be monosemantic, that is, have a single meaning. However, in practice, this rule is sometimes violated. Words with multiple meanings in the vernacular are considered terms when used in a narrow and specific sense in a scientific context. For example, words such as “component,” “structure,” and “model” may have multiple meanings in ordinary speech, but in scientific style they are given a strict definition. In the etymology of terms, metonymy (the use of a close concept instead of a name) or synecdoche (a part instead of a whole, or vice versa) may also occur.

4. Terms are often borrowed words. Most terms, especially technical, scientific or technological terms, are borrowed from other languages. In particular, many terms have entered the Uzbek language from Latin, Greek, Russian and English. For example, words such as hydrolocation, hydrostat, hydromodule have Latin or Greek roots. Also, terms related to art such as theater, drama, novel, dialogue are among the borrowed words.

5. Terms are associated with the scientific style. Terms are mainly used in the scientific style. They are an integral part of official written texts, scientific articles, dissertations, textbooks and encyclopedic works. For example, a monologue is a form of speech by a single person that is consistent, continuous and without the intervention of other people. Such a term is important in scientific and dramatic works.

6. Limited scope of use of terms. Terms are used in a limited socio-communicative context, that is, precisely within their field. They are not widely used in the general language, since their essence and application require special knowledge. This is their main functional limitation. Unlike ordinary words, terms, even when used in general speech, are not always clearly understood.

7. Terms have a naming function. Terms perform only the function of naming (denotation). They are not capable of expressing emotional, figurative, expressive meanings. Terms do not have artistry, content versatility, irony or emotional tone. For example, terms such as “syntax”, “algorithm”, “interference” denote only a certain scientific and technical phenomenon or concept.

8. Structure of terms. According to their structure, terms can be simple, compound, paired or in the form of a word combination.

Simple terms: lexeme, morpheme, chromosome;

Compound terms: radio communication, electronic wave, hydraulic engineering;

Terms in the form of word combinations: nuclear energy, biodiversity, social consciousness.

These various forms indicate the breadth of language capabilities in creating and interpreting terms.

Terms are a unique and complex part of the language system. They should be analyzed not only in the lexicographic, but also in the grammatical, semantic and stylistic layers of the

language. After all, the scientific level of terminological units, the clarity of meaning and the context of use make it necessary to study them in linguistics. Therefore, each term should be analyzed not only as a word, but as an important tool belonging to the system of knowledge of a certain field.

Pedagogy is an integral part of human development, and it performs the function of educating, training the younger generation, preparing them for life, profession and society. The main tool of this process is the word. Through the word, knowledge is transmitted, thoughts are expressed, emotions are expressed, instructions are given and spiritual values are formed. So, the basic tool of the educational and upbringing process is language, and the core element of language is the word.

From this point of view, pedagogy and linguistics are inextricably linked scientific fields. Pedagogical concepts are expressed through language, formed in the mind of the student through language, and applied in practice. This, in turn, requires the correct selection of terms, their scientific justification, semantic understanding, and application in a context-appropriate manner.

The consolidation of pedagogical terms in the Uzbek language, their semantic enrichment, and methodological formation are based on the harmony of linguistics and pedagogical sciences. Language is a means of education, and the term, as an expression of scientific thinking, serves as an important factor in the development of both fields.

Methodological terms are scientific concepts used for language teaching, learning, assessment, planning, determining educational outcomes, and other processes. They are classified as follows:

Didactic terms (e.g., learning outcome, lesson plan, formative assessment);

Pedagogical process terms (scaffolding, differentiation, peer-assessment);

Language skills-related terms (receptive skills, productive skills, fluency).

Several problems are observed when translating terms in the field of education in Uzbek:

Difficulty in finding equivalents: For example, the term scaffolding requires many explanatory translations, since this methodological approach depends on the cultural context.

Multiple use of terms: For example, assessment is sometimes given as "assessment", and sometimes as "measurement of results".

Lack of understanding: Some terms refer to methods that do not exist in the national education system, and it is impossible to translate them directly.

Nationalization of terms should be carried out based on the following strategies:

Contextual translation: terms are not directly translated literally, but explanatory translations are given that are appropriate to their essence (for example, inclusive education - "education that takes into account the needs of all children").

Adaptation: some terms are created in a new form in Uzbek (scaffolding - "step-by-step approach").

Preservation of bilingualism: in some cases, the original term is kept in brackets (for example, "differentiated lesson plan").

It is necessary to develop and constantly update a dictionary of terms for English language teachers.

Uniformity and a list of permitted equivalents should be developed in state standards and curricula.

The translation process requires the cooperation of linguistic specialists and educators.

The development and enrichment of terminology occurs in various ways. First of all, in this process, the adoption of words from other languages, that is, the adaptation of borrowed terms to the language, plays an important role. In addition, the language is enriched by creating new terms from existing words. Also, the gradual acquisition of lexical meaning by some grammatical categories and their transformation into independent words (i.e. lexicalization) is of great importance in the development of terminology.

Another way is the perception of word combinations as a semantically coherent, unified whole, their transformation into terms. This phenomenon is closely related to the dynamic nature of language and the movement of thought in it. For example, expressions such as “artificial intelligence”, “information technology”, although initially simple word combinations, over time have firmly established themselves as special scientific terms.

In the development of terminology, the regular publication of dictionaries containing vocabulary and terms related to special fields is also very important. Such dictionaries not only regulate existing terms, but also serve as a main tool for popularizing new terms and introducing them to the scientific community.

Terminological lexicon is an integral part of the lexicon of the national language, which is formed and develops along with the general development of the language. In this process, scientific and technical, cultural and social changes in society directly affect the terminological system. Therefore, the faster science and technology develop, the more the terminological base of the language is enriched and improved.

As is known, only when any scientific field reaches a high stage of development can it form its own independent terminological system within the framework of the language. This, in turn, is closely related to the word-forming capabilities of the language, the existing lexical resources and the stages of language development. After all, it is not for nothing that the idea that “any scientific thought begins with the development of folk thought and the achievements of the folk language, and is inseparable from it,” is being expressed.

From this perspective, the terminological lexicon not only grows out of the folk language, but also makes a significant contribution to its enrichment, the formation of the scientific method, and the improvement of speech culture. This confirms the existence of a reciprocal, two-way relationship between language and terminology.

It is also worth noting that the issue of creating terminological dictionaries and accurately and meaningfully translating terms from one language to another remains one of the most important and relevant areas of modern linguistics. Especially at a time when globalization is accelerating, information and ideas about scientific and technical progress are being actively exchanged between specialists speaking different nationalities and languages. In such circumstances, accurate and fluent translation of information, clear expression of terms, and their comprehensibility are among the main tools for ensuring international cooperation in the fields of science and technology.

From this perspective, scientific and technical translation requires not only simple translation activities, but also extensive linguistic, cultural and conceptual skills. Because each

term embodies the content of a specific field, and if translated incorrectly, it can distort the essence of an entire scientific idea. This, in turn, can lead to the wrong direction of scientific developments, technical projects or international programs, or even failure. Especially in areas such as engineering, medicine, information technology, where high accuracy is required, incorrect translation of terms can have disastrous consequences.

It should also be remembered that the main support of professional communication in any field is terms. Specialists need to have a single conceptual space in order to exchange ideas with each other clearly and concisely, to fully understand the content. Otherwise, unfamiliar or confusing terms can lead to a breakdown in communication, misunderstandings or errors.

That is, accurate and consistent translation of terms, creation of special dictionaries in the field and their regular enrichment are one of the important conditions for the development of science today. This is relevant not only for linguists, but also for specialists in each field, and is the key to effective and successful organization of scientific information exchange.¹

In conclusion, the adaptation of English methodological terms to national variants is an urgent issue not only of linguistics, but also of educational policy. Their correct translation is of great importance for the accuracy of curricula, professional understanding of teachers and the quality of knowledge of students. A consistent approach, contextual translation and methodological unity are necessary for the nationalization of terms.

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